

Why UAM Needs Real-World Rotor Wake Data

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Abstract

The rise of electric vertical take-off and landing (eVTOL) aircraft brings significant opportunities for urban and regional air mobility. As these aircraft enter low-altitude airspace and operate near people, structures, and other vehicles, understanding the aerodynamic effects of rotor downwash and outwash becomes essential. The flow patterns produced by multi-rotor eVTOLs differ significantly from those of conventional helicopters and present potential safety challenges. Recent measurements of eVTOL rotorwash in hover have demonstrated velocities exceeding recommended safety thresholds at distances greater than typically expected for similarly sized helicopters. These results reinforce concerns about potentially hazardous wind forces generated during takeoff and landing. Additionally, there are enroute concerns regarding the possibility of an eVTOL upset from encounters with trailing wakes generated by emergency or special air missions. This document introduces the reader to rotorwash through basic theory illustrated by empirical data. The need for better measurements is highlighted by recent data collections and requests from regulators and experts. To fill the data gap, we recommend full-scale field measurements using pulsed coherent lidar. These measurements will contribute to developing safety guidelines, infrastructure design standards, and airspace management protocols to support the safe integration of eVTOL operations into the National Airspace System.

1. Introduction

Advanced Air Mobility (AAM) technologies are progressing. AAM encompasses a variety of solutions for low-altitude transportation of people and cargo within high-density urban centers (Urban Air Mobility, or UAM) as well as between regional hubs (Regional Air Mobility, or RAM). Of particular interest is a class of all-electric, multi-rotor UAM aircraft referred to as eVTOL (electric Vertical Takeoff and Landing) aircraft.

Similar to helicopters, eVTOLs take off and land vertically; however, unlike helicopters eVTOLs produce significantly less noise, generate zero emissions during operation, and are expected to be less costly to operate. These advantages have the potential to enable high-volume, high-frequency operations in densely populated urban centers. Because these aircraft will operate in close proximity to people and property during all phases of flight, a broad consideration of potential hazards will help ensure the safe integration of eVTOLs into the Airspace System.

A potential hazard for this new class of aircraft relates to rotor downwash and the resulting outwash occurring during takeoff and landing operations at vertiports and heliports when the downwash interacts with the ground plane. The downwash/outwash (DWOW) associated with helicopters has been studied for many decades; however, experience with conventional single-rotor aircraft cannot be directly applied to eVTOL multi-rotor designs because a multi-rotor system generates more complex flow patterns. Numerical computational fluid dynamic (CFD) simulations of multi-rotor aircraft indicate the existence of “vortex bullets” of high velocity air within the DWOW [1]. A recent study performed for the FAA routinely found DWOW velocities approaching 100 mph for eVTOL aircraft in hover [2]. The characteristics of these higher velocity flows need to be understood – specifically how far they reach from the aircraft, their cross-sectional footprint, and their duration. This information will inform structural requirements of vertiports and permit wind force calculations that can be used to inform lateral and vertical caution zones for maintaining safe takeoff and landing operations.

Flight corridors between vertiports will likely be designated for eVTOL aircraft to maintain safe separations from other aircraft types operating in the airspace. eVTOL aircraft flying within the corridor will be expected to maintain safe separations from each other based, in part, on their trailing wake characteristics. For this reason, NASA is currently involved in a program that may include attempts to measure the trailing wake of eVTOL aircraft using pulsed coherent lidar [3, 4]. Similar attempts to use lidar to measure the trailing wake of helicopters in ground effect have been conducted by the Japanese Aerospace Exploration Agency [5]. In addition to characterizing the trailing wake of eVTOLs, an assessment of the potential for loss of control due to encounters with residual trailing wakes of fixed-wing and helicopter aircraft operating in the same relative airspace should also be investigated. Residual wakes decay very slowly in a low turbulence atmosphere and can be advected by wind potentially placing them in the path of other aircraft.

While significant effort has been devoted over the last fifty years to characterize the trailing wake of fixed-wing aircraft, less research has been conducted to characterize the trailing wake and DWOW of single-rotor aircraft. Even less is known about the flow characteristics of multi-rotor eVTOL aircraft due to their relatively recent introduction.

This paper highlights the need for field measurements of the DWOW and trailing wakes generated by single- and multi-rotor aircraft, with an emphasis on the use of pulsed coherent lidar as the primary measurement instrument. This work will make a significant contribution towards the understanding DWOW and trailing wake characteristics of rotorcraft and support the safe integration of eVTOLs into the NAS.

This document is intended for the scientific community, Air Navigation Service Providers (ANSPs), Regulators, UAM operators, and all relevant stakeholders engaged in developing and implementing the future of urban air mobility.

2. A Need for Field Data

CFD modeling and wind tunnel testing are useful and have contributed to our understanding of multi-rotor systems; however, they have limitations with regard to characterizing the DWOW and trailing wakes of eVTOL aircraft. The fluid dynamics associated with these flows are sufficiently complex that wind tunnel experiments and CFD modeling simply cannot replicate real-world behavior to the degree necessary for developing guidance and standards for safe eVTOL operations.

The DWOW and trailing wake of eVTOL are highly vortical and turbulent making them fundamentally dependent on the Reynolds number of the fluid flow. The Reynolds number represents the ratio of the inertial forces to the viscous forces within the fluid flow. More simply, the greater the Reynolds number the greater the range of scales contained in the turbulence. Wind tunnel tests use scaled models thereby making it difficult, if not impossible, to match the Reynolds number of the experiment to that of the full-scale vehicle. For this reason, wind tunnel testing of eVTOLs may be better suited for measuring forces and moments for the purpose of optimizing, for example, surface aerodynamics, rotor design, and control surfaces, rather than characterizing the turbulent flows generated by these aircraft.

CFD modelling of high Reynolds number flows also presents significant challenges, once again, due to the turbulent nature of the flow field and the wide range of turbulence scales involved. There are a variety of CFD approaches discussed in the literature none of which have been validated for accurately modelling DWOW or trailing wakes of eVTOL or even fixed-wing aircraft. Traditional CFD methods rely on numerical grids and turbulence models to approximate the effects of turbulence without resolving the full range of turbulent scales. A direct numerical simulation of turbulence is not possible for high Reynolds number flows typical of real-world aircraft with today's computational resources. Grid-free methods namely (certain versions of) the vortex particle method (VPM) and the vorticity transport model (VTM) have become popular for high Reynolds number applications. Dr. Richard

Brown of the U.K. company Sophrodyne Aerospace, a strong proponent of VTM, claims the various VPM methods suffer from positional errors of the vortical structures that build up over time. A primary aim of a recent program sponsored by the U.K. CAA was to “verify and validate” Sophrodyne’s VTM modeling of helicopter DWOW [7]. Unfortunately, the data that was collected was not sufficient for this task. Better data will allow CFD modelers to tune their models to better predict DWOW characteristics of single- and multi-rotor aircraft. In all likelihood such data will provide clues that reveal phenomena not accounted for in the models - as was the case with the development of a very accurate wake model for near-elliptical wing loading, which would not have been possible without the high-quality wake data that was collected during the Dubai RECAT program [20, 24, 25].

The need for real-world data to characterize DWOW and trailing wakes is evidenced by the recent data collections that have been reported and those currently underway, as well as calls for data collections from OEM suppliers, regulators, and modeling experts:

As stated in a recent FAA sponsored report [2],

“Full-scale surveys are the most accurate way to determine the velocity of eVTOL DWOW flow fields on the vertiport environment.”

Joby Aviation states in a recent report [8] when referring to various CFD modeling results,

“These are important preliminary studies that highlight the need for experimental data for this new type of aircraft.”

Dr. Richard Brown in a recent article [9],

“In terms of experimental quantification of the outwash...the existence of these compact flow features implies the need for a matrix of test sensors that is spatially far more dense than is currently used for similar measurements of the outwash that is produced by conventional helicopters.”

In a recent U.K. CAA report [7] the authors request access to the FAA eVTOL DWOW data [2] to perform their own analysis and conclude with,

“The complex, transient and vortex-dominated flow needs to be properly understood to ensure safe flight operations.”

During the January 14, 2025 EB105A Vertiport Design Industry Day presentation [11] Robert Bassey, FAA lead engineer for vertiport design, remarks that the FAA will continue to collect data through end of June 2027 to inform the creation of a Unified Heliport/Vertiport Performance Based Advisory Circular,

“FAA is using a data-driven approach to ensure AAM infrastructure standards allow for safe operations. We’ve committed to updating guidance as performance data becomes available.”

In a 2014 report by the U.S. Army Research, Development, and Engineering Command [10] on modeling the rotorwash operational footprint of VTOL aircraft the author states one of the highest priority efforts for future work is,

“The development of a LIDAR type sensor for acquisition of future rotorwash data.”

The author continues,

“It is important to note that a potential exists to dramatically improve the quantity and quality of acquired rotorwash flight test data. This improvement will depend on future investments in Laser Imaging, Detection, and Ranging (LIDAR) sensor technology.”

This review of recent commentary on the introduction of eVTOL aircraft to the NAS highlights the need for full-scale real-world data collections to better characterize the DWOW and trailing wakes of these aircraft. For measuring DWOW the primary emphasis is on spatial resolution. Both experimental observations and CFD modeling have demonstrated that the DWOW flow characteristics can vary significantly over distances less than a meter. Temporal resolution is also important, particularly for characterizing the unsteady “gusty” nature of the flow, which also plays a role in DWOW hazard assessment.

The traditional measurement approach of using anemometers is limited because sufficiently dense arrays can affect the flow measurements downstream (not to mention sufficiently dense arrays are probably impractical to implement). A scanning LIDAR, on the other hand, is non-intrusive and can effectively achieve continuous sampling of the flow field, which, as we will discuss in more detail in Section 3, is well suited for wind force calculations. LIDAR has already been used successfully to measure the strength, decay and transport of trailing wakes from fixed wing aircraft and may be the only instrument capable of measuring the characteristics of eVTOL trailing wakes in cruise and during the transition phase between vertical and horizontal flight.

The future collection and subsequent analysis of real-world DWOW and trailing wake data will inform:

- Infrastructure Design: Vertiports, rooftop pads, and flight corridors must be engineered with accurate DWOW and trailing wake data in mind.
- Flight Safety: Understanding how DWOW behaves around pedestrians, vehicles, and infrastructure is vital to avoid accidents, and characterizing trailing wakes will help inform spacing requirements.
- Model development: e.g., improving CFD modeling methods, modeling of eVTOL DWOW operational footprints.

3. Quantifying Hazardous Winds

The potential hazards associated with rotorwash on people has been studied at least as far back as the 1960s. An extensive reference list of work prior to 1994 is provided in “Rotorwash Analysis Handbook: Volume 1 – Development and Analysis” [12]. One of the conclusions of this work is

“The 30- to 40-knot velocity threshold hypothesis that was first discussed in reference 3 appears to be further validated by recent research work. This hypothesis simply states that the majority of rotorwash-related mishaps can be avoided if separation

distances are maintained so that impacting rotorwash-generated velocities do not exceed 30 to 40 knots across the ground.”

Preston [10] summarizes previous research up to 2014 in his Table 3-1 “*Not-to-Exceed Threshold*” *Outwash Related Hazards*. For Civilian (general population) he defines a Caution Zone when Peak wind velocity is 33.6-44.7 mph, and a Hazard Zone when Peak wind velocity exceeds 44.7 mph (based on Sea Level Standard Atmospheric Conditions), where

“The peak condition relates to the highest velocity or force generated by wind gusts. The mean conditions relate to the average wind encountered.”

Preston further states,

“Recommended limits presented in this section are supported by additional data documented in the attached appendixes. These recommended thresholds are based on available data at this point in time. **Should additional information or research become available, these recommendations should be updated.**”

The sources for the research used to arrive at the civilian limits are summarized in his Appendix C Table C-2. Preston also provides an extensive reference list in his Appendix Q and additional commentary on some of these references in his Appendix R.

The primary takeaway here is the majority of rotorwash incidents can be avoided if winds exceeding 15 m/s (34.5 mph) are isolated from civilians.

In addition to high velocities there is also concern about destabilizing forces, which are sudden changes in force over a very short period of time. One experiment referenced in [12] (p. 151) puts this time period at 400 milliseconds or 2.5 Hz. The recent report by the U.K. CAA [7] subjectively puts this time period at 2-5 Hz. These sudden changes in force can also trigger the human “startle response,” which is an “uncontrollable, automatic, muscle reflex” that can also lead to injury [13].

The following highlights an important point when considering what qualifies as a hazardous wind. Using different data analysis methods Joby Aviation [8] and FAA researchers [2] came to opposing conclusions regarding the radial reach of high outwash velocities. The FAA researchers concluded,

“eVTOL aircraft DWOW at the SA [safety area] and beyond surpass most of the air velocity thresholds found in AC 150/5300-13B, Airport Design (FAA, 2024), and in the FAA Rotorwash Handbook (Ferguson, 1994) (**34.5 mph**).”

while the Joby Aviation authors concluded,

“The measured values show that the design guidance in FAA Engineering Brief 105 for vertiports would result in an oversized requirement for the Joby S4. The smaller requirements for current PPR heliports are sufficient to ensure high outwash velocities are contained within the safety area.”

The opposing conclusions can be attributed to different analysis methodologies.

The FAA report [2] presents velocity statistics for each of the 14 anemometer sensors used based on a sliding 3-second analysis window. The velocity data from each sensor was collected at 40 samples per second (40 Hz) and, other than obvious noise issues, no filtering of the data was performed. The maximum velocity, mean velocity, and standard deviation were determined for each 3-second block of data. The report lists the maximum observed velocity and the maximum observed velocity within two standard deviations of the mean for each sensor. It is important to note here that the velocities listed in the report are the maximums observed over the entire time of observation; however, the total observation time and how often similar maximum velocities were observed by each sensor is not discussed in the report.

The Joby authors [8] used the same 40 Hz velocity data but a different analysis approach:

“The (U, V) velocity components measured by individual sensors were cleaned, reduced to a common 10 Hz sampling frequency, and converted to the outwash velocity magnitudes $V_{outwash} = \sqrt{U^2 + V^2}$.”

The authors plot 15-second averaged velocities and the maximum observed velocity within two standard deviations of the mean (a 15 second observation window is assumed but not stated in the paper). The results of their analysis very much depend on the processes involved in cleaning the data (i.e., removing obvious bad data versus removing spikes in data that may be good), and reducing the data to 10 Hz (i.e., averaging versus decimation). The authors refer to a “10 Hz resolution,” which implies four adjacent velocity samples are averaged to produce a single sample at 10 Hz.

The FAA report concluded the Joby S4 generated maximum outwash velocities that exceeded the 15 m/s threshold in the safety area (a safety area based on 3.0 times the effective diameter of the S4 aircraft), while Joby determined the S4 generated maximum outwash velocities below the 15 m/s threshold in the safety area of the smaller PPR heliport (a smaller safety area based on 2.2 times the effective diameter of the S4 aircraft).

The differing conclusions highlight an important point of consideration. There is no doubt that eVTOL and helicopter rotors produce blade tip vortices and that these tip vortices consist of small-scale high velocity vortex filaments. Vortices by nature are persistent (that is, they decay slowly) and as a result will propagate outward when the rotor downwash interacts with the ground plane. Hence, it is not surprising at all that the FAA report concludes maximum velocities greater than 15 m/s were measured at and beyond the safety area. Recall, Preston states the 15 m/s threshold refers to the peak velocity of wind gusts [10]. The FAA report [2] does not conclude if the high velocities that were measured at and beyond the safety area are associated with large scale gust-like flows or small-scale high velocity vortex filaments generated by the rotor tips. The difference between the two could be the difference between a force that can result in injury and one that will not. The Joby analysis, which reduces the velocity data from 40 Hz to 10 Hz, averages out short duration velocity spikes such as those that would be generated when small-scale rotor tip vortices pass by the anemometer. For a wind to impart a force sufficient to be hazardous the wind field needs to

be spatially and temporally significant. The Joby approach of averaging the velocity stream to 10 Hz (still greater than the 2-5 Hz range associated with destabilizing forces) may offer a more accurate representation of the gust-like nature of the flow, aligning more closely with the intended data product to which the 15 m/s safety threshold should be applied. We will discuss this concept of impulse (force applied over time) more in the next subsection.

Because of the complex nature of the eVTOL outwash, and the fact that high velocities can be associated with the rotor tip vortices, it may be reasonable to use a PAXman-like wind force calculation in which the outwash force is determined at the safety area boundary over some standardized cross-sectional area. The PAXman model is discussed in Section 3 and Appendix C of [10]. A similar approach is discussed in Section 5 of [12]. We summarize the PAXman model in the next subsection and discuss how lidar data may be well suited for this type of wind force calculation approach.

3.1 Wind Force and Impulse Calculation Using LIDAR (Analog to PAXman Model)

The PAXman model was first presented by Silva [26] as part of a CH-47D tandem rotor outwash survey to determine the wind drag force on military personnel exposed to the outwash flow. The PAXman model itself is simply a 10th order polynomial that represents the body half-width of a 6-foot tall person crouched over leaning 20° into the outwash flow, resulting in a projected height of 5.5 feet [10, 14, 26]. The polynomial coefficients are listed in Figure 1 (from Appendix C of [10]) along with a plot of the resulting body half-width curve, x_p , (shown in green) as a function of height, y .

Figure C-4 PAXman Area Distribution (Reference C-18)

a0	4.30939E-01
a1	-4.63972E-02
a2	-1.39649E-01
a3	1.37545E-01
a4	-2.48764E-02
a5	-5.49253E-04
a6	2.21653E-04
a7	-4.18444E-05
a8	1.45194E-05
a9	-7.80009E-08
a10	-1.89822E-07

Table C-3 Polynomial Coefficients (Reference C-18)

Figure 1: PAXman 9th Order Polynomial Body Half-Width Representation of 6-Foot Tall Person Leaning into the Outwash [10] (note, the power associated with the a_{10} coefficient should be 10 and not 9 as is indicated in the figure).

Silva [10, 26] succinctly describes the physical concept of wind exerting a drag force on objects exposed to the outwash flow,

“Personnel immersed in the outwash flow field experience an aerodynamic drag force which is a function of the individual’s size, posture, air density, and the horizontal velocity distribution [of the outwash] with respect to height.”

The drag force calculation proceeds as follows. Figure 2 shows an example outwash velocity profile as a function of height. The symbols indicate the heights at which the velocity was measured using point sensor anemometers. The curves themselves are cubic spline interpolations of the discrete data points.

Figure C-5
Typical Outwash Velocity Profile
(reference C-18)

Figure 2: Example Outwash Velocity Profiles as a Function of Height [10].

The curves are sampled at N equidistant incremental heights, Δy , between 0 and 5.5 feet (the height of the PAXman). The net force on the PAXman is given by the sum of the product of the dynamic pressure ($\frac{1}{2}\rho u_i^2$) and body cross-sectional area ($2x_{pi}\Delta y$) at each incremental height multiplied by the coefficient of drag as

$$F_{PAXman} = C_D \sum_{i=0}^N \frac{1}{2} \rho u_i^2 \cdot 2x_{pi} \cdot \Delta y \quad (1)$$

where C_D is the coefficient of drag, a dimensionless number approximately equal to one ($C_D = 1$), ρ is the air density [slugs/ft³], u_i and x_{pi} are the outwash velocity [ft/s] and the PAXman body half-width [ft], respectively, at incremental height index, i . This calculation can be performed for both the mean wind profile and the peak wind profile.

Based on the PAXman model for military personnel the caution zone threshold corresponds to a mean force of 80 lbs. or a peak force of 87 lbs. The hazard zone threshold corresponds to a mean force of 87 lbs. or a peak force of 115 lbs. [10].

For reference with the civilian safety threshold of 15 m/s we can compute the drag force using Eq. 1 assuming a uniform 15 m/s (49.2126 ft/s) wind. Substitution into Eq. 1 using the full-body cross-sectional area of the PAXman (6.17 ft^2), and standard air density ($0.002377 \text{ slugs/ft}^3$), gives 17.8 lbs. of force (79 Newtons). This is approximately 22% of the military caution zone threshold of 80 lbs based on the mean wind. Performing the inverse calculation, the uniform velocity that corresponds to 80 lbs. of force is 31.8 m/s, which is approximately twice the civilian safety threshold of 15 m/s.

The calculation of Eq 1 is straight forward given the measured outwash velocity profile. The primary assumptions in the accuracy of the calculation are that the interpolated outwash velocities between the measurements are accurate, and the outwash velocity at a given height does not change over the width of the PAXman. The concern with regard to eVTOL aircraft are possible small-scale high velocity jets of air that are not observed due to the coarseness of the sensor array and thus would not be captured by the force calculation. Unlike discrete point anemometer sensors, a vertically scanning LIDAR can continuously observe the flow field in height and stepped horizontally in small increments to provide near-continuous coverage over a desired cross-sectional area. A drag force calculation similar to Eq. 1 is easily extended to two dimensions to account for outwash velocity variation in the cross-sectional plane.

In the next section basic momentum theory is used to provide insight into the velocities one might expect for different rotors geometries (single- and multi-rotor) including small-scale vortical structures. With this in mind, before leaving this section, we can perform one more calculation to get a feel for how much a high velocity small scale structure affects the PAXman force calculation. Here we again consider a uniform 15 m/s wind over the PAXman and include an additional 30 m/s (98.4 ft/s) high velocity small-scale flow with a cross-sectional area of $5.9 \times 10^{-3} \text{ m}^2$ ($6.4 \times 10^{-2} \text{ ft}^2$) consistent with the cross-sectional area of a rotor tip vortex. This high velocity small-scale flow contributes an additional 1.47 lbs. of force, corresponding to an increase of 8.3% over the 17.8 lbs. of force calculated above.

The final point to make here is that the PAXman force calculation does not account for the temporal duration of the various velocity elements (small-, medium-, and large-scale structures). Obviously, a small-scale high velocity jet that exists for a very short time does not carry the same impulse (force multiplied by time) as the same jet persisting for a very long time. Impulse is the change in momentum (in the absence of resistance) corresponding to the application of a force over time.

It seems reasonable that a force calculation similar to the PAXman drag force calculation, possibly using a square reference cross-sectional area rather than the PAXman itself, that includes the determination of the net impulse at a temporal resolution capturing the 2-5 Hz range associated with destabilizing forces, would be a significantly more useful metric than a velocity threshold particularly for eVTOL aircraft generating complex turbulent out flows.

LIDAR not only provides near-continuous coverage in the two-dimensional cross plane it also provides very high temporal sample rates (10,000 to 20,000 samples per second) and encodes the duration of the various velocity elements (small-, medium-, and large-scale structures) in the return signal spectrum. Velocity elements that persist for longer time periods contain greater spectral energy than velocity elements that persist for shorter time periods. A LIDAR that sufficiently resolves the velocity in range captures all that is needed for the force and impulse calculations as suggested by Silva [10, 26],

“PAXman force can be computed for each time step that outwash data was recorded, yielding, in effect, an outwash force time history. This unsteady data can then be postprocessed to provide more meaningful and realistic statistical metrics for outwash force than the previous approach of computing mean and peak forces from the mean and (composite, not instantaneous) peak outwash velocity profiles.”

We conclude this section with Preston’s recommendation [10],

“It is highly recommended that the DoD [Department of Defense] develops an advanced LIDAR type sensor (laser anemometer) for the acquisition of future rotorwash data. The present method of mounting anemometers at several heights on a pole and varying the distance of the pole from the rotorcraft is “antiquated” when considering modern sensor technology. This data acquisition technique acquires a very limited set of velocity data at only several heights above the ground surface. LIDAR technology has the capability to measure a continuous velocity profile from ground level to a specified height within seconds.”

4. Insight into Rotorcraft Downwash/Outwash

Now that we have an understanding of the flow characteristics that may be considered hazardous, we need to have some insight of the downwash and outwash velocities produced by rotorcraft.

Figure 3, taken from [12], graphically depicts the rotorwash of hovering single- and twin-rotor aircraft. The rotorwash consists of three regions: the downwash region, which contains the vertical flow below the aircraft, the outwash region containing radial flow outward, and the transition region between these two. This is a classic figure that has been reproduced by others [6, 9, 10, 14] as it illustrates the important physical properties of the flow that we wish to study.

For the single-rotor, the diagram represents a symmetric flow that radiates outward as the flow interacts with the ground. For the twin-rotor the characteristics are similar except along the line of symmetry between the two rotors where the two flows interact. In this region the diagram depicts a wall of combined flow moving upward and outward. In this region the flow velocities combine (in a mean sense) such that there is zero net velocity along the axis joining the rotors and increased velocity in the wall region compared to that which would be measured for a single rotor. This merging of flows and the resulting higher velocities is the main problem of concern for the multi-rotor eVTOL aircraft [2].

Figure 3: Rotorwash Flow Fields of Single- and Twin- Rotor Configurations Operating in Close Proximity to the Ground [12].

Predicting the velocity distribution of these combined flows is not as straight forward as one might think based on the diagram in the figure. In actuality, the mixing of fluids is, in general, a turbulent process, and to make the problem more challenging the flows that mix are already turbulent from the moment they are generated by the rotor blades. Moreover, the flows are not symmetrical for various reasons that include the presence of a fuselage below the rotor and the rotational direction of the rotor. The resulting turbulent flow is characterized by chaotic oscillations of various scale sizes; large-scale rolling flow is intertwined with small-scale higher velocity rotating swirls and all scales in-between. Characterization of these flows thus requires an understanding of the mean flow as well as an understanding of the temporal/oscillatory nature of the flow. Given such a characterization one can then determine the potential hazards of the flow field.

We can draw insights about the flow velocities by looking at a single isolated rotor using momentum theory (also referred to as actuator disk theory or Rankine-Froude momentum theory) [15, 16]. Momentum theory treats the rotor as an idealized infinitely thin disk that generates thrust by pushing air through itself. By accounting for the work done by the actuator disk and enforcing conservation of mass, momentum, and energy one can calculate, to first order, the mean velocity of the air moving through the rotor disk (near field) and farther downstream (far field).

Referring to Figure 4 the velocity induced by the disk, v_i , as determined using momentum theory is given by

$$v_i = \sqrt{\frac{T}{2\rho A}}, \quad [\text{m/s}] \quad (2)$$

where T [$N = kg \cdot m/s^2$] is the thrust generated by the rotor, A is the area of the rotor [m^2], and ρ is the air density ($\rho = 1.225 kg/m^3$ in the standard atmosphere). In this expression,

the ratio T/A is referred to as the disk loading (typically normalized by standard gravity). The actuator disk generates the induced velocity by producing a pressure differential across the disk. Although there is a pressure difference above and below the disk the velocity of the air mass through the disk is continuous hence the near wake also has a velocity v_i .

Figure 4: Wake from a hovering rotor: (a) out of ground effect (OGE); (b) in ground effect (IGE) [15] (modified to show induced velocity v_i).

Referring to the left panel of Figure 4, enforcement of the conservation laws leads to a reduction in the cross-sectional area of the flow field by one half and a far wake mean velocity equal to twice the induced velocity, $2v_i$. The contraction of the cross-sectional area, referred to as the *vena contracta*, corresponds to a radial reduction of 70.7%. A distance of three to four rotor diameters below the rotor is generally considered to be the beginning of the far wake region; a helicopter operating at heights three to four rotor diameters above the ground is considered to be operating out of ground effect (OGE).

The right panel of Figure 4 captures the main features of the air flow for a single rotor helicopter operating in ground effect (IGE). This diagram shows the contraction of the flow field in the downwash region, an upwash or recirculating flow below the fuselage, and the production of outwash, referred to as a radial wall jet near the ground. These jets have zero velocity at the ground plane and achieve a maximum velocity some height above the ground plane. Our intuition, based on basic momentum theory, is to expect a maximum mean velocity on the order of twice the induced velocity, $2v_i$ as was predicted in the absence of the ground plane.

As mentioned previously, momentum theory provides a first order estimate of the average downwash/outwash characteristics of the rotor. In actuality there is typically significant deviation from the first order predictions due to a host of reasons that include the overall design of the aircraft, the design of the rotor blades, the number of blades, inefficiencies associated with the root and blade tips, and non-uniform inflow.

Figure 5 is a contour plot of the measured mean downwash of a scale model isolated rotor in OGE taken from [17]. The measured downwash is normalized by the theoretical induced velocity given by Eq. 2. This measurement was part of a joint experiment between the U.S Army and NASA Ames Research Center. The left axis is the normalized distance below the rotor (normalized by the rotor diameter) and the bottom axis is the normalized radial distance r/R , where R is the rotor radius.

Figure 5: Flow field velocity contour of a isolated single rotor in hover (OGE) [17].

The mean downwash is shown to reach a maximum of approximately $2v_i$ in agreement with basic momentum theory; however, the flow is by no means uniform as momentum theory predicts. We also note flow recirculation below the blade root cutout around $r/R = 0$ and a persistent velocity deficit around $r/R = 0$ with increasing distance from the rotor, none of which is predicted by momentum theory.

Figures 4 and Figure 7 present measurements of outwash, taken from [18]. This was a joint U.S. Army and NASA test conducted at NASA Langley Research Center’s Rotor Test Cell (RTC) facility using the Army’s General Rotor Model System (GMRS) powered scale rotorcraft model in hover. The scale rotorcraft employs a four-blade rotor with a diameter of approximately 3.4 meters.

Figure 6 shows 2-D plots of the outwash velocity normalized by the induced velocity computed using momentum theory Eq. 2 as a function of normalized height h/R above the ground plane on the left axis and normalized radial distance r/R on the bottom axis, where R is the rotor radius (note that Figure 6 color scaling is different than Figure 5). The five 2-D plots from top to bottom correspond to normalized rotor heights with respect to the ground plane of $z/R = 0.87, 1.14, 1.50, 1.79,$ and 2.0 respectively. The velocity information in Figure 6 is also represented using overplotted scaled velocity vectors that highlight the transition and outflow regions.

Figure 6: Mean normalized outwash velocities and velocity vectors at $C_T = 0.008$ (thrust coefficient) and $\psi = 180^\circ$ (azimuth angle of observation) for different normalized rotor heights z/R [18].

Figure 7 presents this same data graphically for normalized radial distances $r/R = 1.0, 1.25, 1.5, 1.6, 1.7, 1.8, 2.0,$ and 2.5 , which are indicated by the vertical dashed lines in Figure 6. In Figure 7 the left axis is the normalized height above the ground plane, h/R , and the bottom axis is the normalized outwash velocity (normalized by Eq. 2). The normalized rotor heights $z/R = 0.87, 1.14, 1.50, 1.79,$ and 2.0 are indicated by the different colored curves.

Figure 7: Mean non-dimensionalized outwash velocity profiles at $C_T = 0.008$ (thrust coefficient) and $\psi = 180^\circ$ (azimuth angle of observation) at different rotor height ratios z/R for radial station indicated r/R [18].

Summarizing the key results from [18]: for the single rotor scaled model aircraft in ground effect the wall jet maximum mean velocity v_m occurs at a radial distance between $r/R = 1.5$ and $r/R = 1.8$ and has a magnitude approaching $2v_i$, i.e.,

$$v_m = 2v_i. \quad [\text{m/s}] \quad (3)$$

The height above ground, h/R , of the maximum mean velocity ranges from approximately 8% of the rotor radius for normalized rotor height of $z/R = 1$ to approximately 2% of the rotor radius for a normalized rotor height of $z/R = 2$.

The results presented thus far concern the rotorwash mean velocity. As noted earlier the rotorwash is quite variable and hence to better quantify the velocity characteristics one should also include the maximum observed instantaneous velocities.

FIGURE B-2 CH-53E MEAN AND PEAK VELOCITY PROFILES FOR EIGHT 270-DEGREE AZIMUTH RADIAL STATIONS AT A ROTOR HEIGHT OF 37 FEET AND A GROSS WEIGHT OF 70,000 POUNDS (continued)

Figure 8: CH-53E mean and peak velocity profiles at a rotor height of 37 feet ($h/R = 0.94$) and radial stations $r/R = 1.75$ (top) and $r/R = 1.50$ (bottom). For the left axis a height of 12, 8, and 4 feet in normalized distance is $h/R = 0.3, 0.2,$ and 0.1 respectively. For the aircraft characteristics listed in the figure $v_i = 32.5$ knots.

Figure 8 contains two plots from [12, 19], which were part of a series of plots showing mean (open symbols) and peak instantaneous (filled symbols) observed velocity measurements for the heavy lift CH-53E single rotor helicopter at different normalized radial stations r/R . The two plots shown are for radial stations of $r/R = 1.75$ (top) and $r/R = 1.50$ (bottom). These

plots represent the largest magnitude of the mean outwash velocity from the data set. The results shown agree with the key results summarized from model helicopter measurements [17] in terms of the radial station for the maximum mean velocity (between $r/R = 1.5$ and 1.8) and the height of the maximum mean velocity above ground between 2% and 8% of the rotor radius (in this case the maximum mean velocity occurs at a height of 5% to 8% of the rotor radius). For the aircraft characteristics listed in Figure 8, $v_i = 32.5$ knots, which is in agreement with the maximum mean velocity shown in the plots approaching $2v_i$.

Figure 8 also includes data for the observed peak instantaneous velocities (filled symbols). The rotorwash handbook [12] describes a model for the velocity of the large scale “ground vortex.” The model result is indicated by the dashed curve. As can be seen the maximum of the peak instantaneous velocity is nearly 50% greater than the maximum of the mean wall jet velocity. Though it is not specifically stated in [12] the larger scale “ground vortices” are driven by the smaller scale blade tip vortices. These vortex filaments are characterized by high tangential velocities and high axial velocities. The peak tangential velocity, v_θ , of the tip vortex can be estimated using [20]

$$v_\theta = \frac{v_i}{Nf[\ln(4/f) - 0.25]}, \quad [\text{m/s}] \quad (4)$$

where N is the number of rotor blades and f is the ratio of the core radius to the rotor radius.

Table 1 below lists three U.S. eVTOL manufacturer models (Joby S4, Beta Alia-250, Archer Midnight) along with two light helicopters (Robinson R44, Bell 429) and a heavy lift helicopter (Sikorsky CH-53E) ordered by their disk loading. In addition, the table lists the maximum take-off weight (MTOW), the number of rotors, the rotor diameter, and the number of rotor blades per each rotor. These values are taken from publicly available sources and may or may not be accurate. The resulting induced velocity (Eq. 2) and estimated rotor blade tip vortex peak tangential velocity (Eq. 4) are listed in the last two columns.

Table 1: Momentum theory disk loading, induced velocity and blade tip vortex peak tangential velocity estimates for helicopter and eVTOL aircraft

Model	MTOW [kg]	Number of Rotors	Rotor Diameter [m]	Number of Blades	Disk Loading [kg/m ²]	Induced Velocity [m/s]	Tip Vortex Peak Tangential Velocity @ 0.03R [m/s]
R44 R2	1134	1	10	2	14.3	7.6	47.2
Bell 429	3402	1	11	4	35.8	12.0	37.4
Joby S4	2404	6	2.9	5	60.7	15.6	38.9
Beta Alia-250	3174	4	4	2	63.1	15.9	99.3
CH-53E	31,751	1	24.1	7	69.7	16.7	29.8
Archer Midnight	3175	6 6	2	5 2	120.3 48.1 168.4	21.9 13.9 26.0	54.8 86.7 64.9

The radius used for the blade tip vortex tangential velocity listed in Table 1 is 3% of the rotor radius and is based on observations from fixed wing aircraft with near elliptical wing loading [20]. The actual radius of the tip vortex relative to the rotor radius likely depends on the blade load distribution, which is not elliptical for rotorcraft [16]. For reference, decreasing the radius of the tip vortex to 2% of the rotor radius increases the maximum tip vortex velocity to 139% of the listed value, while increasing the radius of the tip vortex to 4% of the rotor radius reduces the maximum tip vortex velocity to 79% of the value listed. We caution that this is a topic in need of additional research – what is presented is simply to provide insight and a starting point for defining requirements of a lidar sensor to measure these flows.

From the table the reader can get a feel for the magnitude of velocities that one might observe in the vicinity of the aircraft near the ground. For a single rotor aircraft, the vicinity is a circle/square 2.5 times the rotor diameter centred on the aircraft. For eVTOL the vicinity is not as well understood because the flows from multiple rotors can combine to produce high velocities (refer to the twin-rotor diagram of Figure 3). In this case the vicinity is a circle/square 2.5 times the effective diameter of the aircraft, D' , centred on the aircraft where D' is defined as “the diameter of the smallest circle enclosing the VTOL aircraft projection on a horizontal plane, while the aircraft is in the takeoff or landing configuration, with rotors/propellers turning, if applicable” [21].

A recent downwash/outwash (DWOW) survey of three multi-rotor eVTOL aircraft performed for the FAA routinely found maximum peak instantaneous DWOW velocities approaching 100 mph (44.7 m/s) while in hover and velocities exceeding the safety threshold 34.5 mph (15 m/s) beyond the recommended safety zone [2]. These velocities are in general agreement with the velocities listed in Table 1 for a rotor tip vortex moving with the induced flow. These measurements were made using a sparse array of sonic anemometers mounted on poles positioned at a single height approximately one meter above the ground while the aircraft hovered with wheels/skids at 1 meter and 10 meters above the ground. A sparse array of sensors at a single height above ground does not provide sufficient resolution to characterize the potential hazard of the flow. For example, a small-scale high velocity vortex filament by itself with a peak velocity of 30 m/s will not produce enough force to be considered a hazard, while a large-scale flow with a velocity less than 15 m/s, such as the trailing wake of a large commercial jet, can overturn an aircraft. Thus, to understand the force potential of these flows it is necessary to make measurements at sufficient spatial and temporal resolutions.

Basic momentum theory can provide insight into the DWOW characteristics for a single isolated rotor. However, this insight is limited because momentum theory does not account for viscosity and cannot directly model three-dimensional vortical flows including blade tip vortices, rotor flow interactions with the aircraft fuselage, or interactions between the flow from multiple rotors. Momentum theory also cannot predict DWOW characteristics when these flows interact with variable turbulent winds near buildings in dense urban environments where these vehicles will be operating, or interact with structures on or near vertiport platforms. In the UAE environment specifically, the higher density altitude means eVTOL aircraft will need to operate at higher thrust settings, which may alter the structure of the rotorwash compared to a lower thrust setting.

5 Pulsed Coherent LIDAR as a Measurement Tool

High fidelity velocity measurements are needed to better understand the rotorwash characteristics of full-scale rotorcraft in the operational environment. Of particular interest are the characteristics of the outwash when in hover near the ground and the trailing wake in both OGE and IGE. With regard to the outwash, the ability to measure the average velocity is important, but also capturing the instantaneous peak velocity and the oscillatory variation of the flow are just as important in terms of quantifying the potential wind hazard.

In 2014 Preston [10] remarked on the potential of a lidar sensor to provide the needed fidelity and recommended development of lidar technology for this purpose after viewing unpublished proof of concept data of continuous wave lidar measurements of the outwash from the V-22 Osprey. To our knowledge there has been only a few lidar based measurement campaigns to measure rotorwash since his call for action [5, 10, 22] and no development of lidar sensors specifically for this application.

Figure 9, taken from [10], is unpublished continuous wave lidar data of the V-22 outwash velocity as a function of height above ground. The lidar data is represented by the two sets of coloured lines, while measurements made with anemometers are indicated by the symbols. Both the average velocity (orange lines and triangle symbols) and peak instantaneous velocity (purple lines and circle symbols) are shown. Preston writes,

“An example of these data is presented in Figure K-86 at distances from the center of the rotor of 92 (top) and 133 (bottom) feet. The V-22 was hovering at a wheel height of 20 feet and the data were acquired along the 90-degree azimuth (single rotor azimuth or non-interaction plane). Data from the V-22 rotorwash test (Reference K-4) that are at approximately the same distance from the rotor are also plotted on the graphs to show general correlation of the data (triangles and circles are the mean and peak velocity points respectively). No efforts were made during the test to attempt to match the exact same V-22 test conditions (i.e. gross weight and wind conditions). The investigators are convinced that this proof-of-concept test met all the standards to justify further development of the LIDAR method for future use in measuring large rotorcraft velocity profile characteristics (i.e. CH-47, CH-53K, and V-22).”

The conventional method of measuring outwash by placing an anemometer at the top of a pole within the region of interest has its advantages and disadvantages. Advantages include the ability to make simultaneous measurements of the outwash velocity at a single point in space (i.e., at a single range and at a single height) many times per second (velocity measurements 100 times a second are common). Although many such sensors can be placed to increase the spatial resolution of the measurements, there is a practical limit to how many sensors can be used at any one time. A dense arrangement of sensors and poles can introduce additional turbulence with high velocity vortical characteristics affecting the velocities measured downstream. Moreover, arranging a dense array of sensors and the associated data loggers can be time consuming and expensive. As we have discussed previously, a sparse

array consisting of fewer sensors can result in not observing high velocity smaller scale flows and also makes wind force calculations impractical.

Figure K-86 V-22 Downwash Velocity Profiles during a 20-ft AGL Hover [unpublished data from Sam Ferguson (EMA) and Robb Lake (NAVAIR)]

Figure 9: Preston’s Figure K-86 from [10]. No additional information is available on the lidar system used or how the data was collected and processed.

Lidar offers several advantages over conventional anemometers for measuring outwash, some of which have already been highlighted so far in this document. Briefly, a compact lidar system is easily portable and can be setup in short order. Unlike anemometers, lidar can remotely measure outwash velocity without disturbing the fluid flow. A pulsed lidar system can provide continuous velocity measurements as a function of range along the laser beam line of sight and can be scanned vertically to capture continuous velocity measurements as a function of height. As a result, the data shown in Figure 9 can be collected within seconds. A scanning LIDAR can also be scan-stepped horizontally to provide near continuous coverage of a two-dimensional cross-sectional area. Additionally, the LIDAR return signal spectrum data product encodes the temporal duration of the various velocity structures (small-, medium-, and large-scale), permitting the calculation of the wind force impulse (i.e., the change in momentum), which is necessary for characterizing destabilizing forces.

Lidar's main challenge in this application (when considering only currently available systems) relates to the system's spatial resolution. The spatial resolution is fundamentally limited by the length of the transmitted laser pulse [23]. If the flow field velocity changes slowly with respect to the length of the pulse, then conventional lidar signal processing can estimate the velocity accurately. However, if the flow field velocity varies rapidly over the length of the pulse, conventional signal processing will give a result that is not representative of the velocity at the point of interest.

To overcome the resolution issue, ideally, one can build a short pulse lidar system specifically for turbulent wind sensing (technically there are no issues preventing this) and then use conventional signal processing, or alternatively, one can work with a longer pulse lidar system that is currently available and employ advanced signal processing methods to extract range resolved velocity estimates at a resolution equal to the system signal sample spacing, which for currently available systems ranges from three meters to less than a meter. Theoretically, range resolved velocity estimates at the sample resolution are possible because the return signal contains all of the velocity information that was observed by the pulse. The challenge is deconvolving the velocity information at the pulse resolution to the sample spacing resolution. This is an active area of research that we are exploring, and have had some success, specifically for this application.

The primary requirements for a pulsed LIDAR for this application include: eye safe, hemispherical scanning, data update rate of 10 Hz or higher, pulse width of 10 ns or less (ideal), pulse energy sufficient to make accurate velocity estimates (which depends on the pulse width, update rate, atmosphere, and LIDAR standoff range), and a velocity bandwidth greater than 45 m/s (100 mph). The currently available commercial systems meet these requirements except for the pulse width. The minimum pulse width available is on the order of 150 ns, which adds an additional requirement that the data product be conducive for postprocessing to enhance the resolution.

Lidar has already demonstrated itself to be a powerful tool for measuring the strength of wake turbulence trailing from commercial jet aircraft. These measurements have been used successfully in recategorization (RECAT) efforts to reduce the minimum safe separation distance between aircraft, thereby increasing capacity at congested airports around the world - including at Dubai International Airport (DXB) [24]. Advanced signal processing techniques, similar to those envisioned for this work, have already been used successfully at DXB during a low-level wake turbulence data collection effort conducted in 2020 during the implementation phase of Dubai RECAT (2019-2020); the results of which led to full implementation of RECAT in February 2021 [25].

6 Proposed Methodology

For the reasons highlighted in this white paper, we propose a coordinated, multi-phase program to measure and analyse downwash, outwash, and trailing wakes of single- and multi-rotor aircraft using pulsed coherent lidar as the primary measuring instrument

beginning with proof-of-concept lidar trials and progressing to full-scale operational measurements.

The deployment of scanning pulsed LIDAR systems represents a strategic and scientifically justified investment for rotorwash and downwash characterization, especially in the context of Urban Air Mobility (UAM) operations in the UAE. While initial costs may be higher than conventional sensors, LIDAR offers unparalleled data quality, operational versatility, and long-term value, making it the most effective solution for eVTOL safety validation and infrastructure integration.

7 Integrating eVTOL Operations with Existing Helicopter Operations (UAE)

In the UAE, helicopter operations are a routine and essential presence in the nation's low-altitude airspace, playing a prominent role in multiple sectors including security patrols, medical evacuations, VIP transport, tourism, offshore logistics, and infrastructure monitoring. These operations are often dynamic in nature, with variable flight paths and mission-critical demands that limit their ability to follow predefined routes.

The expected introduction of eVTOL aircraft, many of which will operate autonomously or semi-autonomously along fixed urban corridors, adds a new layer of complexity to an already active airspace environment. Unlike traditional fixed-wing aircraft, both helicopters and eVTOLs rely on vertical operations and will share overlapping altitudes and manoeuvring zones, particularly near city centres, medical facilities, waterfronts, and designated vertiports.

To ensure the safe coexistence of these aircraft types, a detailed study of their potential interactions is essential. This includes an assessment of:

- **Minimum safe separation distances** between rotorcraft and eVTOLs during hover, take-off, and landing,
- **Wake turbulence and downwash interactions**, especially when operating in close proximity within shared flight paths or near congested vertiport environments,
- **Airspace behaviour during emergency response scenarios**, where helicopters may need immediate and unrestricted access, and
- **Communication protocols and traffic coordination systems** to support real-time situational awareness across both manned and unmanned platforms.

Given the operational diversity of helicopters in the UAE and the technical differences between legacy rotorcraft and next-generation eVTOLs, tailored airspace integration strategies are required. This includes dynamic separation standards, adaptive air traffic procedures, and shared awareness tools that ensure both safety and efficiency.

By proactively studying these factors within the context of the UAE's specific aviation environment, regulators and operators can develop robust frameworks that support advanced air mobility while preserving the critical functions of existing helicopter services.

7.1 Trailing Wake Decay and Advection in UAE Climatic Conditions

A critical safety factor in mixed rotorcraft-eVTOL operations is the behaviour of trailing wakes, particularly their decay rates and advection patterns. These characteristics determine how long and how far the wake remains hazardous after the aircraft has passed, which is particularly important around vertiports with frequent arrivals and departures.

Trailing wakes from eVTOLs consist of complex vortex structures generated by the multiple rotors and the wing tips. The rate at which these wakes dissipate will likely depend on the rotor size, the phase of flight, and the atmospheric turbulence. Slower turning rotors may produce vortical structures with greater circulation strength than faster turning rotors for a given amount of lift. The different phases of flight will likely determine the dominant wake generating source (i.e., the rotors or the wings). In the UAE atmospheric conditions often favour longer wake persistence due to low nighttime and early morning turbulence. Strong thermal inversions in the late afternoon also slow the wake decay and can change the vertical trajectory of the wake, even causing it to stall at altitude.

Wake advection in UAE urban centres is driven by coastal sea breezes, large buildings that can channel and speed up the wake movement, and stratified atmospheric conditions that can potentially trap wakes in the vicinity of rooftop vertiports. These drivers can advect the wakes in an unpredictable manner and thus may require the consideration of mitigation strategies.

Conclusion

As the UAE prepares for the introduction of electric vertical takeoff and landing (eVTOL) aircraft into its urban and regional airspace, it becomes increasingly important to address the aerodynamic implications of this emerging technology. The downwash and outwash produced by multi-rotor eVTOLs raise safety concerns that extend beyond conventional helicopter operations. These concerns are especially relevant during low-altitude flight near buildings, roadways, vertiports, and pedestrian areas. The integration of eVTOL operations within UAE airspace will also need to consider potential encounters with the trailing wakes of emergency and mission-critical aviation activities.

Current modelling techniques and wind tunnel testing are not sufficient on their own to define operational safety margins or infrastructure standards. The real-world spatial and temporal variation of the turbulent flow field produced by eVTOL aircraft necessitates a higher resolution sensing method to more accurately quantify the forces associated with the rotorwash. Pulsed coherent lidar presents a viable method for collecting higher resolution data for this purpose.

A phased, data-driven approach beginning with proof-of-concept lidar trials and progressing to operational measurements will lay the foundation for evidence-based regulation and infrastructure planning. By investing in this work now, the UAE can establish itself as a regional leader in the safe and efficient deployment of advanced air mobility technologies.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declares no conflicts of interest.